

The Douglas Triangle, Prime Roots, and e

A simple rather accurate approximation for e

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Abstract

The Douglas Triangle is a special right triangle with sides $1 : \varphi^2 : \varphi\sqrt{3}$, where φ is the Golden Ratio. Joining two of these on the hypotenuse produces the Douglas Rectangle, which has interesting properties. One such property is a simple yet accurate approximation for e, which differs from e by 0.000000979... . Rewriting the formula gives an equivalent using the first three primes.

Keywords: History of Mathematics, e, prime roots, φ .

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1 The Douglas Rectangle and e

The Douglas Triangle, discussed in [1], can be made into a rectangle by joining two triangles, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Douglas rectangle

We can divide the rectangle into quarters.

Figure 2: Douglas rectangle in quarters

Then, blue ÷ red is an excellent approximation for e.

Figure 3: Douglas rectangle encapsulates an e approximation

$$\frac{blue}{red} = \frac{\phi^2 + 5}{\phi\sqrt{3}} = 2.71828280782816535616\dots$$

$$2.71828280782816535616 - e = 0.000000979369120\dots$$

While this number is not mathematically equal to e, it can be considered equal for use in any applications above nano-scale. If we did not have pocket calculators and computers, and instead did such calculations with an abacus, counting table, slide rule, or via logarithms, and only worked to 3 or 4 decimals, then it would be considered exactly equal to e.

2 Prime roots

$\frac{\varphi^2+5}{\varphi\sqrt{3}}$ can also be written as $\sqrt{15} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}$, or $\sqrt{3}\sqrt{5} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}$.

These alternate forms are noted by Wolfram Alpha (<https://tinyurl.com/mvh9b84s>) but it took some effort for me to find the proof. I eventually found it by working backwards, which revealed the various “non-obvious” steps. Algebra with φ frequently requires lateral thinking as well as familiarity with the assorted identities associated with φ , and thus would be educationally beneficial to include in mathematics courses. Whoever built Giza certainly used φ a lot more than we do.

Proof:

Remember that $\varphi^2 = \varphi + 1$, and $\varphi = \frac{\sqrt{5}+1}{2}$. Thus $\sqrt{5} = 2\varphi - 1$.

$$\frac{\varphi^2 + 5}{\varphi\sqrt{3}} = \frac{\varphi + 6}{\varphi\sqrt{3}} \quad (1)$$

$$= \frac{6\varphi - 5\varphi + 6}{\varphi\sqrt{3}} \quad (\text{Sneaky move}) \quad (2)$$

$$= \frac{6\varphi + 6 - 5\varphi}{\varphi\sqrt{3}} \quad (3)$$

$$= \frac{6(\varphi + 1) - 5\varphi}{\varphi\sqrt{3}} \quad (4)$$

$$= \frac{6\varphi^2 - 5\varphi}{\varphi\sqrt{3}} \quad (5)$$

$$= \frac{6\varphi - 5}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (\text{Divide through by } \varphi) \quad (6)$$

$$= \frac{6\varphi - 3 - 2}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (\text{Sneaky move}) \quad (7)$$

$$= \frac{3(2\varphi - 1) - 2}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{3\sqrt{5} - 2}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (\text{See } \sqrt{5} \text{ above}) \quad (9)$$

$$= \frac{\sqrt{3}\sqrt{3}\sqrt{5} - 2}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (\text{Sneaky move}) \quad (10)$$

$$= \frac{\sqrt{3}\sqrt{3}\sqrt{5}}{\sqrt{3}} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (11)$$

$$= \sqrt{3}\sqrt{5} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (12)$$

Thus we can approximate e using the first three primes.

Bibliography

- [1] I. Douglas, ‘The Douglas Triangle, Khufu and Khafre’, Zenodo, 2021-12-30. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5810431. [Online]. Available: <https://zenodo.org/record/5810431> (visited on 2022-01-01).